

Impaired emotion recognition in *Cntnap2*-deficient mice is associated with hyper-synchronous prefrontal cortex neuronal activity

Short title: Prelimbic cortex-associated impaired emotional recognition in *Cntnap2*-KO mice

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Dataset and codes repository links

ESPi raw data <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10453363>

SxP raw data <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10453918>

Free raw data <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10453219>

SP raw data <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245899>

Cntnap KO optoEphy <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12943749>

Fig 1 Behav vids <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12819775>

DeepPhenotyping codes <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10232645>